

Making the Right to Stay work for local communities

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Expert insight from AEIDL work in EU Territorial Cohesion contributes to the formulation of the new EU Right to Stay Strategy.

At the end of 2026 the European Commission will launch the Right to Stay strategy, one of its landmark initiatives of the present EU term. This initiative, stemming from the initial recommendations of the [Letta report](#) about the need to ensure that the EU internal market does actively help people to move or stay, as was further described in the [von der Leyen's political priorities for the upcoming mandate](#) “in the place they call home”. This discussion paper builds on evidence and emerging recommendations from several Horizon Europe projects—[SMART ERA](#), [BEATLES](#), [FUTURAL](#), [GRASS CEILING](#) and [RURBANIVE](#)—which collectively provide insights into the design and implementation of smart, sustainable and inclusive local development policies across the European Union. It draws on the European Association for Innovation in Local Development (AEIDL)'s long-standing work on place-based policy, community-led development and territorial cohesion, in line with its [Strategic Plan \(2025\)](#) and priorities for the 2024–2029 EU term.

The analysis is further informed by extensive policy research and exchanges with practitioners, regional and local authorities, and European institutions. In particular, it builds on the discussions and outcomes of the [ELIF webinar on the Right to Stay: Understanding the drivers of territorial cohesion](#) (4 June), which brought together over 270 participants, including representatives from the European Commission (DG REGIO), the European Parliament, regional stakeholders and EU-funded projects. The insights from this exchange provide a strong empirical and policy basis for the arguments developed in this brief.

This contribution should be understood primarily as a **technical synthesis of ongoing analytical work**, intended to inform the European Commission's reflection process on the Right to Stay. This will be eventually built upon and translated into a AEIDL policy statement to be adopted at a later stage, reflecting wider organisational positions. At this stage, the objective is to provide **evidence-based, delivery-oriented insights** to support the development of coherent, place-based and operational

policy responses that might inform the forthcoming EU strategy.

Framing the Right to Stay within the European Territorial Model

The Right to Stay should be understood as a **complement to freedom of movement**, not a contradiction of it. Both the Letta Report and the Commission political guidelines rest on the idea that citizens should have the genuine possibility to build their lives where they choose, rather than being structurally pushed to relocate due to unequal access to opportunities, services or infrastructure. Domestic constitutions distinguish between negative rights (e.g. freedom of movement, freedom of speech) and positive rights (where the state does not refrain itself but acts to provide the conditions to exercising of those rights, be that housing, welfare policies, etc.). While equating the EU Treaty goals with domestic constitutional rights would be far-fetched, a similar distinction could apply to distinguish between freedom of movement and right to stay. The latter would be then fully consistent with Article 174 TFEU and the Union's objective of economic, social and territorial cohesion (Art 3 TEU), which together explicitly recognise the need to address disparities between regions, including rural, peripheral and demographically declining areas and address the inequalities defined in the [European Charter for Fundamental Rights](#) and the [European Pillar of Social Rights](#).

Rather than framing it as a new individual right, the Right to Stay is more usefully understood as a **policy and delivery challenge**. The key question is not whether citizens formally enjoy the freedom to stay in the place of their choice, but whether EU and national frameworks actually provide the **conditions that make staying a viable, attractive and sustainable option**. From this perspective, the newly minted Right to Stay would act as a **test of delivery capacity**, assessing whether policies translate into tangible improvements in everyday life at local and functional territorial level.

This approach builds on a broader EU policy lineage—from the Territorial Cohesion acquis to recent debates on demographic change and territorial imbalance—but shifts the focus from conceptual recognition to **operational effectiveness**. Where policies remain misaligned with territorial realities, or where implementation prioritises compliance over outcomes, the Right to Stay risks remaining abstract.

Europe's **polycentric territorial structure** is central to this analysis. The Union is not defined by a single dominant urban core, but by a dense network of functional urban areas, small and medium-sized towns, villages and functional areas that act as everyday anchors for economic activity, service provision and social life. These territories are not marginal; they constitute the structural backbone of European cohesion. This makes a **place-first delivery model both feasible and necessary**, grounded in local realities, participatory governance and territorial evidence.

At the same time, the ability to remain in a given territory is not determined by a single factor, but by the **combined performance of interconnected systems**—services, labour markets, mobility, housing and governance. The Right to Stay therefore emerges from an **ecosystem of conditions**, rather than from isolated sectoral interventions.

Drivers and Barriers: Why Staying Is Not Always a Real Choice

The decision to stay or leave is shaped by a complex interplay of structural and experiential factors. Evidence shows that the Right to Stay depends on the **availability, accessibility, affordability and quality** of essential services and socio-economic opportunities, rather than on employment alone. In this context, small and medium-sized towns play a crucial role as **“everyday anchors”** within wider functional areas, providing first-line access to services, employment and social life. Their weakening—through demographic decline, service withdrawal or underinvestment—can trigger cascading effects across entire regions.

Access to Essential Services

At the core of staying decisions lies access to essential services, understood not as infrastructure provision in itself, but as **functional usability in daily life**. This includes healthcare, childcare and education, social services, mobility, digital connectivity and housing. Where these services are not available within reasonable time, cost and quality parameters, territorial inequalities become progressively entrenched, particularly in low-density and demographically declining areas.

A key implication is the need to move from infrastructure-based evaluation towards **outcome-based metrics**, focusing on travel time, affordability, reliability and user experience. The gradual withdrawal or degradation of services—often incremental—can create self-reinforcing

cycles that ultimately push individuals to relocate. In response, there is growing evidence supporting the establishment of **minimum service baselines**, adaptable to national contexts but ensuring a consistent level of access across territories.

Labour Markets and Economic Opportunities

Labour market dynamics remain central but must be understood in a **territorial context**. Many regions simultaneously experience labour shortages and unemployment due to persistent skills mismatches, limited diversification and weak career pathways. Demographic ageing exacerbates these challenges while increasing demand for essential services.

Beyond job availability, the ability to stay depends on the **overall economic attractiveness** of territories, including productivity, innovation capacity and market access. Regions experiencing decline often face cumulative disadvantages across these dimensions. This highlights the need to connect service provision with **place-based economic strategies**, supporting SMEs, the social economy and local innovation ecosystems. In this context, EU initiatives such as [Harnessing Talent](#) underline the importance of ensuring that Internal Market dynamics do not inadvertently reinforce territorial imbalances.

Mobility and Connectivity

Mobility constitutes a **foundational enabling condition**. Without affordable, reliable and multimodal transport options, access to employment, services and social participation is severely constrained. The emerging concept of transport poverty captures this reality, shifting attention from infrastructure provision to the effective ability to reach opportunities.

In many low-density regions, conventional transport systems fail to provide adequate coverage, reinforcing isolation. As the concept of transport poverty becomes embedded in EU and national frameworks, it is likely to shape the design and evaluation of public transport obligations and accessibility standards. Mobility must therefore be understood as a matter of **territorial fairness**, closely linked to broader service provision systems.

Source: Thomas P. / Pexels, free to use.

Source: DC Studio / Magnific, free-to-use image.

Housing and Cost of Living

Housing systems play a decisive role in shaping staying decisions. Territories face diverging patterns, from **vacancy and degradation in shrinking areas to affordability crises in more dynamic regions**. These dynamics constrain both the ability to remain and the possibility of return migration.

Addressing these challenges requires integrating housing into **broader spatial and demographic strategies**, including the reuse of existing stock, development of flexible housing models and alignment with mobility and service provision. At the same time, environmental quality, energy affordability and climate resilience are becoming key determinants of territorial attractiveness, particularly for vulnerable populations.

Demographic and Social Dynamics

Demographic change represents a **structural transformation of territories**, affecting labour supply, service demand and social cohesion. Patterns of outmigration are often selective, disproportionately affecting young people, skilled workers and women, thereby weakening local innovation capacity and accelerating ageing dynamics.

These processes also have a **strong territorial and political dimension**. Areas experiencing prolonged decline often develop a sense of neglect and loss of agency, contributing to what has been described as a **“geography of discontent”**. Addressing the Right to Stay is therefore not only a socio-economic objective, but also a matter of **democratic resilience**, requiring policies that restore territorial fairness, visibility and trust.

Defining decline: towards a common territorial baseline

A key challenge for operationalising the Right to Stay lies in the **absence of a consistent and actionable territorial framework** to identify and monitor decline. There is growing recognition that programming and performance tracking—particularly under future National and Regional Partnership Plans (NRPPs)—should build on existing European statistical classifications such as **DEGURBA** and **TERCET**, allowing for clearer identification of priority areas at a sufficiently granular level. At the same time, flexibility remains necessary, as Member States and regions often rely on more advanced or fine-grained systems, including composite indicators and neighbourhood-level data.

Equally important is the development of **territorially anchored service metrics**, enabling policymakers to assess access not only in terms of provision but in terms of **distance and usability**. Approaches based on travel-time thresholds (e.g. 15–30–60 minutes access to services) illustrate how a future **catalogue of essential services** could be planned, monitored and compared across territories. Existing analytical work and pilot practices demonstrate the feasibility of such approaches.

A more systematic integration of **functional geographies** is also required. Understanding where people live, work and access services—across functional urban and rural areas—is essential for aligning policy design with real territorial dynamics. While different methodologies coexist at EU and national level, there is increasing need for a **minimum common mapping framework** covering the entire Union.

Finally, the definition of demographic decline itself remains insufficiently harmonised. While recent policy

developments have introduced new benchmarks, these have not yet translated into a shared operational standard across funding frameworks. Moving towards a **common baseline definition of demographic decline**, adaptable to national contexts, would strengthen targeting, comparability and policy effectiveness.

In this context, the notion of “**smart shrinking**” should be **reframed as “smart adaptation”**: a strategic approach focused on maintaining functionality, access to services and quality of life, rather than assuming inevitable decline. This implies a more active and coordinated role for public policy at both EU and national level.

Why Local Action Is Central to the Right to Stay

The Right to Stay cannot be delivered through top down, sectoral policies alone. It requires a **fundamental shift in governance**, placing local actors and territories at the centre of policy design and delivery. Local action is essential not only for tailoring interventions to territorial realities, but also for ensuring that policies translate into **tangible improvements in people’s everyday lives**.

A key strength of local and place based approaches lies in their ability to generate **continuous feedback loops between policy design, implementation and lived experience**. Because interventions are tested in real conditions and adjusted in real time, local governance reduces the risk of persistent policy mismatch and allows learning to be embedded in practice. By contrast, centralised delivery models often rely on delayed feedback and more rigid structures, making adaptation slower and more costly.

In this context, “local” should not be understood solely as a spatial scale, but as a **distinct governance model**, based on participation, co production and partnership. Established frameworks such as **Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI)**, **LEADER** and **Community Led Local Development (CLLD)**, along with domestic forms of local governance, demonstrate how this approach can enable stakeholders to identify priorities, combine funding sources flexibly and support experimentation and innovation. Local action therefore operates where needs are directly observable and solutions can be tested and refined, making it a **core delivery mechanism** for the Right to Stay.

The effectiveness of these approaches depends critically on the quality of **partnership arrangements across the entire policy cycle**, including preparation, implementation, monitoring and evaluation. Strengthening the partnership principle should therefore be seen not only as a governance objective, but as a **necessary condition for effective delivery**. When stakeholders are meaningfully involved, policies are better targeted, implementation is smoother, and outcomes are more sustainable.

A distinctive asset of many European territories — particularly small towns and rural areas— is the

presence of strong **social capital**, including trust-based relationships, dense local networks and informal cooperation mechanisms. These assets enable communities to mobilise quickly, co design solutions and adapt interventions to real needs, creating dynamic feedback loops that are often absent in large-scale systems. Recognising and strengthening social capital is therefore a **strategic priority** for territorial policy.

Local action also plays a crucial role in strengthening **trust and democratic resilience**. When citizens experience EU policies through visible and relevant improvements in their local environments, trust in institutions increases. Conversely, when policies remain distant or abstract, perceptions of neglect and disconnection can reinforce territorial discontent. In this sense, local delivery is not only a technical issue, but a **political instrument** for reinforcing cohesion and legitimacy.

Extensive evidence from EU programmes and research projects confirms the effectiveness of place based approaches. Local areas function as **laboratories for innovation**, where integrated solutions—such as **Smart Villages**, social service innovation or community led energy initiatives as well as EU wide initiatives such as the **EU Rural Pact**—can be developed and replicated. Evaluations consistently show that bottom up governance, mobilisation of social capital and cross sectoral collaboration are often more decisive for long term success than the scale of individual investments.

These approaches are also particularly effective in reaching **vulnerable groups** and addressing complex challenges, from service provision in ageing regions to inclusion in rural economies. Moreover, local governance structures have demonstrated their value in **crisis response and resilience**, including climate adaptation and emergency coordination.

Taken together, this evidence suggests that the Right to Stay ultimately depends on the capacity to **embed policy delivery within local ecosystems**, supported—but not replaced—by national and European frameworks. Strengthening local action, partnership and community capacity is therefore not a complementary measure, but a **central pillar of an effective Right to Stay strategy**.

Governance, Policy Coherence and Delivery Capacity

Achieving the Right to Stay is fundamentally a question of **governance and delivery capacity**, rather than the introduction of new policy objectives. Persistent territorial disparities often arise not from a lack of strategic intent, but from misalignments between policy design, governance structures and local implementation realities. Strengthening these delivery conditions is therefore essential to translating ambition into measurable territorial outcomes.

A central consideration is the need to evolve towards

more **integrated and multi-layered governance approaches**, where responsibilities are clearly articulated, coordination across levels is effective, and information flows support timely decision-making. In this perspective, the effectiveness of territorial policy depends not only on vertical coordination between European, national and regional levels, but also on **horizontal cooperation across sectors and stakeholders** within territories. Ensuring that partnership approaches remain meaningful and operational across the policy cycle is a key enabling condition for this transition.

At the same time, **administrative complexity** continues to represent a significant barrier to effective delivery. Where rules, procedures and reporting requirements vary across instruments operating in the same territory, implementation risks becoming compliance-driven rather than outcome-oriented. Simplification—through greater alignment of rules, clearer allocation of responsibilities and more integrated approaches to funding—should therefore be understood as a **strategic facilitator of place-based delivery**, particularly for smaller municipalities and local actors with limited administrative capacity.

Source: AEIDL.

Ensuring greater coherence across policy frameworks is also essential. The relationship between cohesion objectives and broader EU frameworks—such as the **Single Market, State aid rules, public procurement systems and other regulatory instruments shaping economic activity**—deserves particular attention. Strengthening complementarities across these domains can help ensure that **economic integration and territorial cohesion operate as mutually reinforcing objectives**, rather than creating unintended tensions. In practice, this points to the value of more territorially sensitive interpretations and coordinated implementation of existing frameworks, allowing policies to respond more effectively to diverse local conditions while preserving core EU principles.

A further priority concerns the alignment between **policy scales and functional territorial realities**. Many

interventions continue to be designed around administrative boundaries that do not fully reflect how people access employment, services and mobility in practice. Greater attention to functional areas and territorial diversity can help ensure that policies are more closely aligned with lived geographies, thereby improving their effectiveness and relevance.

In this context, the integration of **demographic dynamics into policy planning and delivery** is particularly important. While demographic change is widely recognised, its implications are not always systematically reflected in programming, allocation or performance frameworks. Strengthening the role of demographic analysis can support more forward-looking and territorially responsive interventions, especially in areas facing sustained population decline or ageing dynamics.

Effective delivery also depends on the role of **intermediary actors and local capacities**. Organisations operating at the interface between policy frameworks and local communities play a critical role in translating objectives into practice, coordinating stakeholders and adapting solutions to specific contexts. Supporting these capacities can enhance the overall effectiveness and inclusiveness of policy implementation.

Closely linked to this is the need to improve **data systems and monitoring approaches**. Moving towards more outcome-oriented frameworks—focusing on accessibility, affordability, quality of services and user experience—can provide a more accurate picture of how policies affect people's daily lives. Enhancing the availability and usability of territorially disaggregated data, while maintaining proportionality, can strengthen both accountability and policy learning.

The importance of **long-term planning and policy stability** should also be underlined. Structural challenges related to demographic change, service provision and territorial inequality require sustained and coherent responses over time. Predictable frameworks support investment, enable local planning and increase the likelihood of lasting impact.

Finally, the integration of **digital transformation and innovation into territorial approaches** remains a key opportunity. Ensuring that all regions can effectively participate in the green and digital transitions requires attention not only to infrastructure, but also to skills, governance capacity and the ability to embed innovation within local ecosystems.

Taken together, these considerations suggest that the Right to Stay can be most effectively supported by improving the **coherence, targeting and delivery of existing policies**, rather than by introducing new instruments. Strengthening partnership-based governance, simplifying implementation, aligning policies with functional geographies, enhancing local capacities and ensuring consistency across policy frameworks—including those governing markets, investment and public intervention—

can collectively contribute to more balanced and resilient territorial development.

In this context, tools such as [Territorial Impact Assessments](#), including [rural proofing](#), play an increasingly important role in supporting evidence-based, multilevel decision-making. Moving towards more coherent and compatible approaches to assessing territorial impacts—while building on existing practices—can help ensure that policies are better adapted to diverse territorial conditions and contribute effectively to the broader objectives of European cohesion.

Moving forward

AEIDL will continue engaging in this strategy once it is published by the European Commission and its practical implementation via new EU policies and the **National and Regional Partnership Plans (NRPPs)** will be discussed in future ELIF meetings as well as through our Horizon Projects' dedicated spaces for policy exchange such as the RURACTIVE Forum, the RURBANIVE Forum, FUTURAL Rural Innovation Forum (EU-RIF) and other specific events.

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